

Adaptive Control of Time-varying Systems based on Parameter Set Estimation

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Abstract

Adaptive control of time-varying plants, in the presence of unmodeled dynamics and bounded disturbances, via parameter set estimation is proposed. The set estimator uses normalization and maps the uniformly bounded equation error on parametric error, which characterizes the modeled part of the plant. Based on the information from the set estimator, a switching control criterion selects the parametric vector from a set of nominal model parameters and tunes in the adaptive controller. At the same time, through stabilization against the parametric error, the policy renders the closed-loop modeled dynamics robust with respect to the equation error mechanisms.

Notation

The volume of an ellipsoid \mathcal{E} is denoted as $\text{vol } \mathcal{E}$. The cardinal number of a finite set Ψ is $\text{card}(\Psi)$. The identity matrix in \mathbb{R}^n is denoted as \mathbf{I}_n . Similarly, the zero vector in \mathbb{R}^n is $\mathbf{0}_n$ and the zero matrix in $\mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2}$ is $\mathbf{0}_{n_1 \times n_2}$. Given a matrix M , its modulus matrix is denoted as $|M|$ and its Hermitian part as $(M)_S$. The k -th column of M is denoted as $\text{col}_k(M)$. In addition, its largest (smallest) singular value is $\sigma_{\max}(M)$ ($\sigma_{\min}(M)$), and its smallest eigenvalue is $\lambda_{\min}(M)$.

1 Introduction

Developments in the field of bounded-error estimation, such as the methods of parameter bounding [1, 2] and set membership identification [3, 4], have motivated novel approaches toward the adaptive control of discrete-time systems. Based on a priori knowledge of the equation error bounds, the new methods tackle the problem of the adaptive stabilization of the entire membership set.

Despite the common goal, the literature work in this

emerging field lacks a unified framework. Among several pioneering efforts, construction of a parameter set estimator, for adaptive control, that takes account of unmodeled dynamics and bounded disturbances is given in [5]. An approach to predictive self-tuning by parameter bounding is developed in [6]. The feasibility of optimal control design in the presence of parametric uncertainty and additive disturbance is investigated in [7]. Other works include adaptive versions of existing robust control designs, such as Hurwitz's method [8] or dual control in a bounded error context [9].

The literature, however, has offered but an incomplete analysis of this methodology. First, based on the assumption of the uniform boundedness of the equation error, the issue of bounded signals in the main adaptive loop has been considered implicitly resolved. The assertion that sample-by-sample stability of the closed loop guarantees bounded signals in the presence of the bounded disturbance that causes the equation error, warranted the absence of a detailed analysis. In addition, many practical problems involve relatively bounded rather than uniformly bounded equation error. Indeed, if the control design is based on a reduced-order model, then relatively bounded unmodeled dynamics are present. Second, there is lack of provisions for the analysis of the main adaptive loop whenever the parameters of the plant model vary with time. Of course, this problem hampers the vast majority of adaptive control methodologies.

The objective of this paper is to address the problem of adaptive control of time-varying discrete-time systems, against bounded disturbances and unmodeled dynamics, via Parameter Set Estimation (PSE). Herein, a recently developed PSE algorithm [10], which tracks time-varying parameters, is enhanced with the ability to map uniformly or relatively bounded modeling error on parametric error using the technique of normalization [11, 12]. The parametric error, in the form of an ellipsoid, connects with the adaptive con-

troller via a grid of nominal parameters. For every node and associated nominal model of the grid, the control parameters that place the poles of such models at a common desired location are computed. Each nominal closed-loop model possesses a local robustness measure that spans about the corresponding node of the grid in the form of an orthotope. When the ellipsoid travels over the grid, tracking time-varying parameters, there are several orthotopes that enclose the membership set. By certainty equivalence, the adaptive controller tunes in to the center of one such orthotope.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an outline of the method. In Section 3, we propose a modified SMID algorithm in the presence of unmodeled dynamics and an estimation-based switching policy to control the identified set of modeled dynamics. The stability of the adaptive system against the different error mechanisms is discussed in Section 4. The paper concludes with an example and simulation results that demonstrate the main features of this approach.

2 Method Description

The approach exploits the property of the PSE methodology that maps the bounded equation error on parametric error. The latter, called the membership set, is expressed in terms of the ellipsoid

$$\mathcal{E}(\bar{\theta}, \bar{P}) = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{2n} : (\theta - \bar{\theta})^T \bar{P}^{-1} (\theta - \bar{\theta}) \leq 1, \right. \\ \left. \bar{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}, \bar{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}, \bar{P} > 0 \right\}$$

where θ is a vector of the plant model parameters. To use effectively the information on the parametric error, the controller is tuned to parameters outside as well as inside the membership set; thus, deviating from conventional certainty equivalence. The control parameters, $f(\theta)$, where the mapping f depends on the underlying control design, are adjusted for stabilization of the entire membership set or guaranteed performance for every model within the membership set. In principle, such a control strategy is computationally inefficient for adaptive control and, at the same time, inconvenient for the purpose of analysis.

To overcome this, the method tunes the control parameters to nominal values, $f(\theta^{(l)})$, at each node, $\theta^{(l)}$, of a parametric grid, Θ° . These control parameters are computed off-line, that is, outside of the adaptive loop. The parametric grid extends over an area such as the hyper-rectangle

$$\mathcal{H} = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{2n} : \theta_j^{\min} \leq \theta_j \leq \theta_j^{\max}, j = 1, \dots, 2n \right\}$$

where parametric drifts or jumps are anticipated. The nodes of the grid

$$\theta^{(l)} = [\theta_1^{(l)}, \dots, \theta_{2n}^{(l)}]^T, \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, \text{card}(\Theta^\circ) \quad (1)$$

are generated as follows

$$\theta_j^{(l)} = \theta_j^{\min} + \kappa(l, j) \cdot \delta, \quad j = 1, \dots, 2n \quad (2)$$

for some $\delta > 0$ and an integer $\kappa(l, j) \in [1, \frac{\theta_j^{\max} - \theta_j^{\min}}{\delta}]$. Centered about every nodal point, the method defines the orthotope

$$\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}) = \left\{ \theta \in \mathcal{H} : \theta_j^{(l)} - \varepsilon \leq \theta_j \leq \theta_j^{(l)} + \varepsilon, j = 1, \dots, 2n \right\}$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$.

At each sample, the ellipsoid, $\mathcal{E}(\bar{\theta}, \bar{P})$, interfaces with the parametric grid, Θ° . This procedure yields the tuning set, Θ , which is the set of all nodal points whose orthotope encloses the current membership set. The characteristic feature of the control adaptation is the stabilization of the membership set without solving for the stabilizing controller at each step, but through switching among the set of control parameters, $f(\Theta)$. Figure 1 depicts the main idea of the proposed adaptive system. Therein, y is the system output, u the input, u_r the external command input, and e the modeling error.

Stability considerations require the size, ε , of the orthotopes to be smaller than the local robustness measure, ϑ , of the nominal control design, $f(\theta^{(l)})$, and, at the same time, larger than the average size of the ellipsoid, $\mathcal{E}(\bar{\theta}, \bar{P})$. The resulting scheme avoids the drawbacks that have hampered the indirect adaptive control design such as singularities in the identifier and on-line solution of the Diophantine equation.

3 Set Membership Identification

Consider the linear time-varying system

$$A(\theta^*(t), z^{-1})y(t) = B(\theta^*(t), z^{-1})u(t) + d(t) + \varpi(t) \quad (3)$$

where $A(\theta^*(t), z^{-1}) = 1 - a_1^*(t)z^{-1} - \dots - a_n^*(t)z^{-n}$, $B(\theta^*(t), z^{-1}) = b_1^*(t)z^{-1} + \dots + b_m^*(t)z^{-m}$, z^{-1} is the unit delay operator, $y(t)$ is the system output, $u(t)$ is the system input, $d(t)$ is the system disturbance, and $\varpi(t)$ corresponds to unmodeled dynamics.

Equation (3) can be rewritten as

$$y(t) = \theta^{*T}(t)\phi(t) + d(t) + \varpi(t) \quad (4)$$

where $\theta^*(t) = [a_1^*(t) \dots a_n^*(t) \quad b_1^*(t) \dots b_m^*(t)]^T$ is the true parameter vector and $\phi(t) = [y(t-1) \dots y(t-n) \quad u(t-1) \dots u(t-n)]^T$ is the regression vector. The variations in parameter vector $\theta^*(t)$ are described by

$$\theta^*(t+1) = \theta^*(t) + w(t) \quad (5)$$

where $w(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is the parameter disturbance vector and $r = 2n$.

The system disturbance $d(t)$ and the parameter disturbance vector $w(t)$ are assumed to satisfy the following bounds

$$|d(t)| \leq \eta \quad (6)$$

$$w^T(t)R^{-1}(t)w(t) \leq 1 \quad (7)$$

where η and $R(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ are known at each time t . The matrix $R(t)$ is symmetric positive definite and represents an ellipsoidal bound on the possible parameter vector deviations during each time step. The modeling error $\varpi(t)$ is relatively bounded [13], that is,

$$|\varpi(t)| \leq \nu m(t) \quad (8)$$

where $m(t) = \sigma_0 m(t-1) + |u(t-1)| + |y(t-1)|$, $\nu > 0$, $0 < \sigma_0 < 1$, and $m(0) \geq 0$.

Let the equation error $v(t) = d(t) + \varpi(t)$, and define the following normalized variables: $\bar{v}(t) = \frac{v(t)}{1+m(t)}$, $\bar{y}(t) = \frac{y(t)}{1+m(t)}$, and $\bar{\phi}(t) = \frac{\phi(t)}{1+m(t)}$. Equation (4) can be rewritten in terms of the normalized variables as

$$\bar{y}(t) = \theta^{*T}(t)\bar{\phi}(t) + \bar{v}(t). \quad (9)$$

It is easy to show that the normalized equation error is bounded as

$$|\bar{v}(t)| \leq \gamma \quad (10)$$

where $\gamma = \eta + \nu$.

The normalized system, as described by equations (5) and (9) and bounds (7) and (10), is directly amenable to the Optimal Volume Ellipsoid algorithm for Time-Varying systems (OVETV) [10]. The OVETV algorithm computes an ellipsoid

$$\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} = \{\theta(t) : (\theta(t) - \tilde{\theta}(t))^T \tilde{P}^{-1}(t) (\theta(t) - \tilde{\theta}(t)) \leq 1\}$$

with center $\tilde{\theta}(t)$ and symmetric positive definite matrix $\tilde{P}(t)$. This ellipsoid is guaranteed to contain the true parameter vector $\theta^*(t)$ for all time t . In addition to this guarantee, the algorithm seeks to minimize the volume of $\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}$ at each time step t . This minimization is critical for the feasibility of the adaptive control design.

To achieve these objectives, the algorithm combines the optimal volume time update equations of [14] with the optimal volume measurement update equations of [15, 16]. Assume that $\theta^*(t-1) \in \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t-1), \tilde{P}(t-1)\}$ at time $t-1$. The optimal time update equations solve

$$\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} = \arg \min_{\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} \supset G(t)} \text{vol } \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} \quad (11)$$

where

$$G(t) = \{\theta(t) : (\theta(t) - \theta(t-1))^T R^{-1}(t-1) (\theta(t) - \theta(t-1)) \leq 1, \theta(t-1) \in \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}\}$$

The set $G(t)$ contains the estimates of $\theta^*(t)$ that are consistent with the variation in the parameter vector from time $t-1$ to time t . This set is easily derived from equations (5) and (7).

The optimal measurement equations solve

$$\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} = \arg \min_{\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} \supset \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\} \cap \tilde{F}(t)} \text{vol } \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}; \quad (12)$$

where

$$\tilde{F}(t) = \{\theta(t) : |\bar{y}(t) - \theta^T(t)\bar{\phi}(t)| \leq \gamma\}$$

The set $\tilde{F}(t)$ contains the estimates of $\theta^*(t)$ that are consistent with the measurements at time t . This set is easily derived from equations (9) and (10).

If $\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(0), \tilde{P}(0)\}$ is chosen such that $\theta^*(0) \in \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(0), \tilde{P}(0)\}$, the solutions to (11) and (12) provide a recursive algorithm that guarantees that $\theta^*(t) \in \mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}$ for all time t . The solutions to (11) and (12) are given as follows.

3.1 Time Update Equations

The solution to (11) is given as follows [14].

1. Solve the generalized eigenvalue problem

$$R(t-1)x_j = \lambda_j \tilde{P}(t-1)x_j$$

for each λ_j , $j \in [1, r]$.

2. Solve

$$\sum_{j=1}^r \frac{1}{\lambda_j + p} = \frac{r}{p(p+1)}$$

for the unique $p > 0$.

3. Then, the solution to (11) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\theta}(t) &= \tilde{\theta}(t-1) \\ \tilde{P}(t) &= (p+1)\tilde{P}(t-1) + (p^{-1}+1)R(t-1) \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Measurement Update Equations

The solution to (12) is given as follows [16].

1. Set

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\alpha} &= \max \left(\frac{\bar{y}(t) - \tilde{\theta}^T(t)\bar{\phi}(t) - \gamma}{(\phi^T(t)\tilde{P}(t)\phi(t))^{1/2}}, -1 \right) \\ \bar{\alpha} &= \min \left(\frac{\bar{y}(t) - \tilde{\theta}^T(t)\bar{\phi}(t) + \gamma}{(\phi^T(t)\tilde{P}(t)\phi(t))^{1/2}}, 1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

If $\underline{\alpha} \geq 1$ or $\bar{\alpha} \leq -1$, then the observed data is inconsistent with $\mathcal{E}\{\tilde{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}$ and the algorithm stops.

2. Set $\epsilon = \underline{\alpha}\bar{\alpha}$. If $\epsilon \leq -\frac{1}{r}$, then no measurement update is necessary, that is

$$\bar{\theta}(t) = \tilde{\theta}(t) \quad \bar{P}(t) = \check{P}(t).$$

3. Set $\mu = \frac{\underline{\alpha} + \bar{\alpha}}{2}$.

4. If $|\mu| > \rho$, then

$$\begin{aligned} b &= 2r\mu + \frac{1+\epsilon}{\mu} \\ \tau &= \frac{b - \text{sign}(\mu)\sqrt{b^2 - 4(r+1)(1+r\epsilon)}}{2(r+1)} \\ \sigma &= \tau\left(\tau - \frac{1+\epsilon}{\mu}\right) + 1 \\ \varsigma &= \frac{\sigma}{1 - \frac{\tau}{\mu}} \end{aligned}$$

5. If $|\mu| \leq \rho$, then $\tau = 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \max(|\underline{\alpha}|, |\bar{\alpha}|) \\ \sigma &= r\alpha^2 \\ \varsigma &= \frac{r(1 - \alpha^2)}{r - 1} \end{aligned}$$

6. Update $\bar{\theta}(t)$ and $\bar{P}(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\theta}(t) &= \tilde{\theta}(t) + \frac{\tau\check{P}(t)\phi(t)}{(\phi^T(t)\check{P}(t)\phi(t))^{1/2}} \\ \bar{P}(t) &= \varsigma\check{P}(t) + (\sigma - \varsigma)\frac{\check{P}(t)\phi(t)\phi^T(t)\check{P}(t)}{\phi^T(t)\check{P}(t)\phi(t)} \end{aligned}$$

For numerical reasons, ρ is chosen to be a very small value in steps 4 and 5 and is used to determine when $\underline{\alpha} \approx -\bar{\alpha}$.

4 Adaptive Control Design

Once we complete the identification step, the current information on the parameter uncertainty is quantified in the ellipsoid $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}$. In turn, this enables the tuning of the controller parameters within the finite set of values designed for each node of the grid Θ° . Let the controller be given as

$$R(\hat{\theta}(t), z^{-1})u(t) = S(\hat{\theta}(t), z^{-1})y(t) + u_r(t) \quad (13)$$

where $R(\hat{\theta}(t), z^{-1}) = 1 - \sum_{q=1}^n r_q(\hat{\theta}(t))z^{-q}$, $S(\hat{\theta}(t), z^{-1}) = \sum_{q=1}^n s_q(\hat{\theta}(t))z^{-q}$, and $u_r(t)$ is an external command input. Denote as

$$f(\theta) = [s_1(\theta) \quad \dots \quad s_n(\theta) \quad r_1(\theta) \quad \dots \quad r_n(\theta)]^T$$

the mapping from the plant to the controller parameters. The controller parameters $f(\theta)$ are tuned among the nodal points in Θ° whose orthotopes include the entire ellipsoid $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}$.

4.1 Switching Criterion

Formally, the tuning set is defined as

$$\Theta(t) = \{\theta^{(l)} \in \Theta^\circ : \mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}) \supset \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}\}.$$

Note that the maximum and minimum values of the i th coordinate of $\theta(t)$, where $\theta(t) \in \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}$, are given by $\bar{\theta}_i(t) \pm \sqrt{\bar{P}_{ii}(t)}$ [17]. Define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}), \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}) &= \\ \epsilon - \max_{i=1 \dots r} (\sqrt{\bar{P}_{ii}(t)} + |\bar{\theta}_i(t) - \theta_i^{(l)}|) \end{aligned}$$

A nodal point $\theta^{(l)}$ will be in the tuning set $\Theta(t)$ iff $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}), \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}) \geq 0$. If $\theta^{(l)}$ is in the tuning set $\Theta(t)$, $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}), \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\})$ is simply the minimum distance from the ellipsoid $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}$ to the boundary of the orthotope $\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)})$.

Thus, $\hat{\theta}(t)$ will be chosen based on the following criterion:

$$\hat{\theta}(t) = \arg \max_{\theta^{(l)} \in \Theta(t)} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}), \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \bar{P}(t)\}) \quad (14)$$

That is, we are choosing the node whose bounding orthotope ‘‘best’’ encompasses the ellipsoid. For other possible criteria, see [18].

4.2 Stability Analysis

Using the notation $e(t) = \theta^*(t) - \hat{\theta}(t)$, the main control loop of the adaptive system, in state-space form, is

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(t+1) &= (F(\hat{\theta}(t)) + \sum_{j=1}^n e_j(t)E_j)\phi(t) \\ &+ \begin{bmatrix} \bar{0}_n \\ 1 \\ \bar{0}_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} u_r(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \bar{0}_{2n-1} \end{bmatrix} v(t) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where the system matrix

$$F(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta^T \\ \mathbf{I}_{n-1} \mid \mathbf{0}_{(n-1) \times (n+1)} \\ f^T(\theta) \\ \mathbf{0}_{(n-1) \times n} \mid \mathbf{I}_{n-1} \mid \bar{0}_{n-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

and the perturbation matrices

$$E_j = \begin{bmatrix} \text{col}_j^T(\mathbf{I}_{2n}) \\ \mathbf{0}_{(2n-1) \times 2n} \end{bmatrix}$$

As shown in reference [18], the following sufficient conditions guarantee the stability of equation (15). First, there exists $P > 0$ such that

$$(\rho')^{-2} F^T(\theta^{(l)}) P F(\theta^{(l)}) - P < 0, \quad \forall \theta^{(l)} \in \Theta^\circ \quad (16)$$

where $0 < \rho' \leq 1$. Second, the local robustness measure

$$\vartheta = \frac{1}{2} \min_{\theta^{(l)} \in \Theta^\circ} \frac{-b_0(\theta^{(l)}) + \sqrt{b_0^2(\theta^{(l)}) + a_0 \cdot c_0(\theta^{(l)})}}{a_0} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= 2n \cdot \sigma_{\max}(|P_{ee}|), \quad [P_{ee}]_{ij} = (E_i^T P E_j)_S \\ b_0(\theta^{(l)}) &= \sigma_{\max} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |(F^T(\theta^{(l)}) P E_j)_S| \right) \\ c_0(\theta^{(l)}) &= \sigma_{\min}((\rho')^{-2} F^T(\theta^{(l)}) P F(\theta^{(l)}) - P) \end{aligned}$$

satisfies the following inequality

$$2\vartheta > \varepsilon \quad (18)$$

where ε is the half width of the orthotopes $\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)})$.

To establish the feasibility of the switching criterion (14), conditions that guarantee the tuning set, $\Theta(t)$, to be nonempty are warranted. Reference [18] shows that the cardinal number $\text{card}(\Theta(t)) > 0$, if the distance between adjacent nodes in the grid $\delta < \varepsilon$ and the average diameter of the ellipsoid, $2\frac{\nu+\eta}{\sqrt{\zeta}}$, satisfies

$$2\frac{\nu+\eta}{\sqrt{\zeta}} < \varepsilon \quad (19)$$

where $\zeta \leq \lambda_{\min}(\tilde{P}^{-1}(t))$ for all t . The size of the orthotopes that satisfies both conditions (18) and (19) exists and is easily obtained if

$$\vartheta > \frac{\nu+\eta}{\sqrt{\zeta}}$$

This last condition relates the local robustness measure with the magnitude of the disturbance, the magnitude of the unmodeled dynamics, and the persistency of excitation in the system.

5 Example

Consider a system described by equation (9) with

$$\begin{aligned} a_1^*(t) &= 1.525 + 0.02 \sin(0.02t) \\ a_2^*(t) &= -1.0 \\ b_1^*(t) &= 0.975 + 0.02 \cos(0.02t). \end{aligned}$$

The open loop system is not only time-varying, but marginally stable as well. Our control objectives are to guarantee stability of the time-varying system and to improve its transient performance.

Knowledge of the true parameters is required neither for identification nor control. However, for set membership identification, the bounds in (7) and (10) must be known. We set $\gamma = 0.01$ and $\xi = 4e^{-4}$ where $R(t) = \xi^2 I$ and I is the identity matrix. The initial ellipsoid, $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(0), \tilde{P}(0)\}$, must contain $\theta^*(0)$ and was chosen with $\tilde{P}(0) = 10I$ and $\hat{\theta}(0) = 0$.

For the control system design, the parametric grid Θ° must be specified. The grid was defined over the following area: $a_1(t) \in [1.5, 1.55]$, $a_2(t) \in [-1, -0.95]$,

and $b_1(t) \in [0.95, 1.00]$ with the grid spacing δ set to 0.01. This results in a set of $6^3 = 216$ nodes in Θ° .

At each grid node, a controller of the form in (13) was designed to place the closed-loop poles at $\{0, 0, 0, 0.3 \pm 0.5i\}$. Closed-loop stability is guaranteed if the conditions in (16) and (18) hold. The condition in (16) was checked and is satisfied for all nodes in Θ° as defined above. The local robustness measure in (17) was calculated to be $\vartheta = 0.0219$. From (18), ε , which is one half the width of the orthotopes, must be less than 0.0438.

The output of the system, $y(t)$, is shown in Figure 2. For this simulation, the reference input, $u_r(t)$, chosen to be a square wave with a period of 40 time steps. A plot of the parameter $a_1(t)$ is shown in Figure 3. The plot contains the actual parameter, $a_1^*(t)$, the center estimate of the ellipsoid, and the upper and lower bounds that are found by projecting the ellipsoids onto the coordinate axes. The distance between the upper and lower bounds must be less than 2ε . For this simulation, it took three times steps for the ellipsoid $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}$ to shrink from its initial ellipsoid, $\mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(0), \tilde{P}(0)\}$, which was very large (assuming almost no knowledge of the true parameters), to an ellipsoid that fits in one of the orthotopes defined above. Then, the condition, $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{O}(\theta^{(l)}), \mathcal{E}\{\hat{\theta}(t), \tilde{P}(t)\}) \geq 0$, was satisfied for all $t > 3$.

6 Conclusion

The paper has proposed a novel approach to the indirect adaptive control of linear discrete-time systems. The design is able to track time-varying parameters and is robust against bounded disturbances and unmodeled dynamics. To accomplish this, the new method uses parameter set estimation and stable switching over a set of controllers with sufficiently large local robustness regions.

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Figure 1: The adaptive system.

Figure 2: System output with square wave input.

Figure 3: Parameter $a_1(t)$ with square wave input.